

Research Article

Investigating nurses' intention to use electronic health records: The Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology approach

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Abstract: Technology integration into the public healthcare sector is considered one of the pipeline projects to enhance healthcare proficiency and productivity. As such, there has been huge investment in the health domain geared towards successfully integrating health technology among health professionals all in the quest to achieve better health delivery services and universal health coverage. User acceptance of such technology as electronic health records has become necessary for the productive deployment of the health sector innovations. The study adopted the Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology and additional constructs of attitude and design aesthetics to investigate nurses' intention to use electronic health records, as they form part of the direct users of the technology. A field investigation was carried out with 381 nurses from diverse medical institutions in Ghana. The study used a quantitative approach anchored on the structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis to verify that, performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, attitude, and design aesthetics, all have a substantial positive impact on nurse's electronic health records adoption intention. The results of the analysis indicated the behavioral intention (BI) of nurses to use electronic health records was predictable by Performance Expectancy (PE) ($\beta = .194^{**}$, $p < 0.01$), Effort Expectancy (EE) ($\beta = .261^{***}$, $p < 0.001$), Social Influence (SI) ($\beta = .377^{***}$, $p < 0.001$), Attitude (ATT) ($\beta = .380^{***}$, $p < 0.001$) and Design Aesthetics ($\beta = .217^{**}$, $p < 0.01$). The findings confirm that the UTAUT model has predictive potential and viability. The study implications are discussed based on empirical findings.

Keywords: *Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT), Health Technology; Electronic Health Records; Nurses; Ghana*

Introduction

The twenty-first era has witnessed a fast-growing use of computers in many areas of human activities. Manual ways of handling processes are gradually shifting to the use of computers and their applications. Medicine, commerce, industry, finances, and education have experienced a great transformation in the use of computers. Current innovative technologies defy the outmoded methods of accomplishing tasks and rendering of a particular service. In recent times, Information Communication Technology (ICT) saturates several fields and serves as an avenue for growth in production and an increase in revenue (Basu & Fernald, 2007). Because of the rapidly growing infiltration of computers, made possible through the use of the ICT (Chinn & Fairlie, 2007) numerous studies have shown the positive effect of ICT and its applications adoption such as creating significant world differences, productive capacity, alleviating poverty, viable development and quality health delivery (Arkorful, Shuliang, Muhideen, Basiru, & Hammond, 2019; Puri, 2007; Tsai et al., 2019; Walsham, 2001). Michiels and Van Crowder (2001) have classified ICT as a spectrum of electronic technology that is flexible, adaptable, able to transform, and reshape entities once merged in new configurations. ICT keeps revolutionizing our lives, our aspects of interacting with one another as well as daily activities and work. Its framework in the health domain is conceptualized broadly as electronic health (e-health), which comprises telemedicine, electronic health records, e-prescription among others.

To address the concerns of patients, the efficiency of healthcare operation is becoming progressively critical to satisfy and maintain clients. Technologically, the proficiency of medical operations has become imperatively important to be improved to address the increasing healthcare challenges (Alhashem, Alquraini, & Chowdhury, 2011; Arasli, Ekiz, & Katircioglu, 2008). Patients' interest in hospital services is growing as living conditions are evolving and demand is being made for quality healthcare to improve lives. This has stirred an amount of urgency on the healthcare provider to invest hugely in advance IT services in the health domain, to meet the needs of their patients and service users. Health technology offers a wide range of opportunities, higher performance, and results (Eysenbach & Jadad, 2001; Napoli, 2001). These opportunities are referred to as electronic health services and include the availability of regular medical data, e-

prescription, medical decision support systems, excellently-planned data sharing between divisions, improved health service delivery, and medical care preservation (Ludwick & Doucette, 2009; Meier, Fitzgerald, & Smith, 2013).

While the positive effects of the health technology are highlighted by these observations, they do discuss inherent dynamics and the contextual cues characterizing their use. Over the years, scholars and clinicians have tried to define factors that facilitate decisions on technology adoption and usage. However, the relative usage and integration of modern technology across various domains which comprise the individual, institutional and inter-institutional levels have rendered the process complex (Merrell, 2013; Sugarhood, Wherton, Procter, Hinder, & Greenhalgh, 2014). Some scholarships have associated challenges arising from the individual levels as societal, cultural, economic, legal, and ethical barriers. They also attach a lack of knowledge about the advantages of these ICT applications (i.e. e-health which includes electronic health records), low usage skills, interconnection limitation, and security concerns as the challenges from the institutional level (Currie & Seddon, 2014). In the view of Hu and Bentler (1999), the growing investment in ICT by medical organizations across the globe has highlighted users' acceptance as a pressing concern as these users are central both in the technology implementation and in its management. In the same vein, several studies have reported a high-level failure and rejection in reforms using ICT in different fields with the health sector not excluded in these setbacks (Aarts & Gorman, 2007). A probable cause linked with the failure is that, institutions have yet not adequately understood factors that impact individuals intention to embrace technological innovations (Aarts & Gorman, 2007; Giuse & Kuhn, 2003). Indeed, users' acceptance and utilization of a technological system together constitute the most significant aspects that lead to effective technology operation (Selder, 2005). There is a growing pattern in hospital records as several health facilities are incorporating ICT to manage and ensure efficient health record-keeping and sharing data through electronic health records. This is due to the potency of these systems to adequately curb the several health challenges that exist, by means of avoiding duplication and loss of patient data, wrong diagnostic reports among others. The development, approval, and usage of ICT services are quite a complex function and has necessitated various studies trying to bring to light the challenging factors that impede the implementation and acceptance of the ever-increasing ICT based services, especially in the health domain (Maass & Eriksson, 2006). According to (Hamidfar, Limayem, & Zegordi, 2008) the usage of IT application and systems among medical professionals is relatively low

especially in emerging countries. In trying to understand why individuals may use a technology and identifying the underlining factors is paramount in helping to ensure that the technology is effectively adopted and used. Nurses play a vital role with regard to patients' health records taking, and sharing the data collected with physicians for the necessary medical assistance to be offered to the patients. Given the key role of nurses in healthcare, they form vital part in technology usage and indeed, their acceptance and use are considered crucial indicators of the system's successful implementation (Hilz, 2000).

Considering the similar but separate identifiers indicated in previous research, the adoption of technology is driven by certain characteristics that include user-related features, technological, social, cultural, and economic aspects. Therefore, it is important to be familiar with and at the same time to recognize the factors that have an impact concerning health technology deployment of any form of corporate innovation strategic plan, particularly in countries where technological progress and use are emerging (Achampong, 2012). This makes health technology adoption worth exploring. Drawing from the urgency with which health concerns need to be handled and on a broader scope, the attainment of health for all, technology deployment, adoption, and utilization, has gained attention in the research domain. Several studies have endeavored to discover and explain adoption intention concerning technology (Arkorful et al., 2019; Hossain, Quaresma, & Rahman, 2019; Sherer, Meyerhoefer, & Peng, 2016).

For various studies, including operations management, the UTAUT theory has been used (Badewi & Shehab, 2016; Zhang & Dhaliwal, 2009). Hoque and Sorwar (2017), employed the partial least square method (PLS), premised on Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) together with an extended Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model in their research. The scholars sampled 300 participants and the aim was to empirically examine the key determining aspects that impact the acceptance of mHealth services by old people. The findings showed that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, technology anxiety, and resistance to change are sufficiently linked with users' behavioral intent to embrace mHealth operations. However, the research found no substantial association between the facilitating condition and the willingness of users to adopt the mHealth operations. In another seminal study, the researchers incorporated UTAUT predictors for examining home care patients and clinician's approval of telemedicine equipment. The results showed a clear association between the UTAUT model and

behavioral intent (BI) for the use of telehealth devices. These studies confirm the potency of the UTAUT to effectively predict the adoption intention of health technology. The current study looks a step further at the design aesthetic of the electronic health record technology on adoption intention. This study describes design aesthetics as how the color, shape, size, and appearance of electronic health innovation systems and tools may provide certain artistic, sense of proportion, or attract one's emotions (Cyr, Head, & Ivanov, 2006). Design aesthetics are intended to induce users' attention and augment deployment and implementation desire (Hsiao, 2013). Jeong, Kim, Park, and Choi (2017) also asserted that design aesthetics is an attractive feature of some systems, which influence its adoption and use. Against this background, investigating reasons that impact electronic health records adoption intention by nurses using the Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology approach is of much importance to scholarship and policy. The research significantly contributes to the literature and in so doing, help achieve nationwide health access which is geared towards addressing all sort of disparity in health care delivery and ensure effective and efficient health provision.

Electronic Health Records (EHR)

In recent times, proper data management, storage, and retrieval of patients' health records are very important in overall healthcare delivery to ensure patient safety and treatment. In this regard, Berg and Toussaint (2003) assert that healthcare systems should possess smart search functions, instant location access functions, and data integration capabilities to enhance easy health data sharing and interoperability. That is the correct approach forward, as this intervention will not only help overcome deep-rooted shortfalls in the health sector record-keeping but will in the same vein stir up an appreciable dosage of efficiency and effectiveness in records keeping and health delivery services in general. Critical to a successful electronic health record adoption in the various health setting in different countries is stakeholder engagement. Stakeholders are seen not only as a source of knowledge but as people and institutions that can assist in directing the decision-making process as a key part of the selection development. Regarding this study, stakeholders of electronic health records systems are the category or class of entities who are actively or passively engaged in the deployment, application, and use of the systems in the health setting. Stakeholders comprise a wide array of classification ranging from government, private and public healthcare practitioners (nurses, doctors, laboratory technicians, midwives, health administrators), clinical research organizations,

pharmaceutical industry actors, etc. For this study, the research seeks to concentrate on nurses who constitute the fulcrum of electronic health record use.

Interest groups (stakeholders) and researchers alike keep appreciating the central role of electronic health records integration in the health domain. This is mostly due to the numerous benefits linked with the integration and usage of health technology. Electronic health records are an emerging technology from the developed world (Acquah-Swanzy, 2015) which facilitates not only patient-health practitioner interaction across diverse health systems, but also significantly deepens inter and intra-system interaction. In the views of Christodoulakis, Asgarian, and Easterbrook (2017), whereas private service providers may perceive the electronic health records system as a profit-making system, actors within the pharmaceutical industry may regard the same system as a distribution system. Moreover, the government may also consider the system as a set of policy systems instituted to address specific issues in health. Health seekers may equally consider the system as a resource structure. To researchers and local community members, electronic health records may be considered as a complex system and a social support system respectively. System users and providers of health-related services on the other hand may regard electronic health records as a market system. Health workers may also attribute the system as an enabling tool. Knowing the responses of stakeholders' perspectives would help in providing relevant insights into what goes to inform the formation of these perspectives. Equally, it would also help to establish an informed and empirical relationship between stakeholders' perceptions, and health information technology systems. A significant benefit of electronic health record systems lies in accessing information wherever and whenever it is needed. Another benefit is that the electronic system guarantees continuous participation and a constructive dialog among medical professionals, management, and ICT experts. The interoperable EHRs form the basis for health information systems that help other systems like e-prescription, e-booking, administration, management, or operations. EHR permits the exchange of organized health data between approved health stakeholders to enhance healthcare quality and to save significantly (Fernández-Alemán, Señor, Lozoya, & Toval, 2013). The implementation of EHR involves numerous benefits, including cost savings, enhanced care quality, promotion of validated medications, records managements and finally agility (Fernández-Alemán et al., 2013). EHR is therefore considered an economically effective technological advancement that improves performance (Häyrinen, Saranto, & Nykänen, 2008). To build a solid foundation through policy and programs to ensure the integration of such

health technology intervention, the government of Ghana enacted the electronic health strategy in 2010. The aim was to:

- (a) Augment the health materials and data governance structure
- (b) Develop the aptitude of the health sector for a broader health intervention
- (c) Enhance access and bridge disparities in the health sector by ICT use, and
- (d) Eliminate the traditional paper record reporting in the health domain (Afagbedzi, Obuobi, Aryeetey, & Bosomprah, 2013; Arkorful et al., 2020).

Even though there exists policy infrastructure to drive electronic health technology, of which electronic health records are a component, research outcomes confirm snail pace adoption. The assumption, therefore, is that perhaps the implementation of a policy framework may not be enough. This, therefore, begs the question, is policy infrastructure enough to drive electronic health records adoption in Ghana? In addition to policy, which other factors are pertinent to accelerate electronic health records adoption among nurses? Against this backdrop, the researchers sought to investigate nurses' intention to use electronic health records, using the UTAUT.

Theoretical Framework and Hypothesis Development

Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

This study seeks to investigate nurses' intention to use electronic health records using an extended Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology model. There exist several theories of technology acceptance, and a number of these theories have been pragmatic in the health sector (Holden & Karsh, 2010). The unified theory of acceptance was proposed by Venkatesh in 2003 and it is an amalgamation of eight different technology acceptance theories (Kijisanayotin, Pannarunothai, & Speedie, 2009; Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, & Davis, 2003). In a longitudinal study to validate the UTAUT, it concluded that UTAUT variance in intention to use was 70% (Venkatesh et al., 2003) which is far higher than other theories which accounted for just 40% (Kijisanayotin et al., 2009). As shown in previous research, the UTAUT can be employed to explain the behavioral intent of using a specific technology e.g. (Magsamen-Conrad, Upadhyaya, Joa, & Dowd, 2015; Parameswaran, Kishore, Li, & management, 2015; Venkatesh et al., 2003). The core elements of this theory comprise four primary building blocks that are significant predictors of

intention and usage behavior. They include performance expectancy (PE), effort expectancy (EE), social influence (SI), and facilitating conditions (FC) (Holden & Karsh, 2010). The UTAUT has been a basic model for the field of technology adoption since it was developed and has been evaluated in numerous settings, including health information systems. For this study, the researchers adapted three of the original constructs of the model namely performance expectancy (PE), effort expectancy (EE), social influence (SI) together with two additional constructs which are attitude towards electronic health records and Design aesthetics (i.e. appearance) to have a modified UTAUT.

Research Model and Hypotheses

Hypothesis Development

This study explored the approval of electronic health records (EHR) by nurses in some selected Ghanaian hospitals, based on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). The fundamental focus of the UTAUT model is to predict the behavior intent of users of technology through four primary variables (i.e. PE, EE, SI, and FC). The model for this research adopted three central variables of the UTAUT model (PE, EE, SI) together with two additional constructs attitude (ATT) and design aesthetics (DA) to anticipate behavioral intention (BI) to use electronic health records by nurses (see figure 1). This research draws on previous behavioral intention studies aimed at using technology by concentrating on electronic health records usage. Also, this research uses a statistical modeling approach to test the UTAUT as a behavioral intent predictor (i.e. structural equation modeling). The various constructs are explained below and subsequently the study hypotheses:

Performance expectancy (PE)

Perceived Expectancy according to this study is described as the seeming practicality of technology, specifically, the extent to which the users (nurses) think that the usage of electronic health records will aid in accomplishing their healthcare duties efficiently and enhance their effectiveness. Performance expectancy is theoretically and analytically comparable to perceived usefulness from TAM (Venkatesh et al., 2003). By extension, it also refers to the relevance of a system or an object (i.e. electronic health records) to an individual in realizing a goal or an objective. The conceptualization of performance expectancy converges around the notion that

individual decision to either use or stick to technology, is principally hinged on the pertinence and capability of the said item or object to help realize a goal or set of goals. This suggests that the more useful individuals find a technology, the greater the likelihood for them to demonstrate a positive behavior towards the technology. Technological acceptance research in other areas has repeatedly shown that the probability of embracing technology increases if participants consider technology to be useful (Holden & Karsh, 2010; Venkatesh et al., 2003). This assertion is reiterated by Kim and colleagues that perceived usefulness impacts, attitudes, and intention to use technology (Kim, Han, Yoo, & Yun, 2012). Based on this we proposed that;

Hypothesis 1: Performance expectancy has a significant effect on nurses' behavioral intentions to adopt electronic health records.

Effort expectancy (EE)

Effort expectancy is the level users of electronic health records believe the use of the system will be devoid of difficulty. Effort expectancy is theoretically linked to perceived ease of use from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Previous studies have found that a significant indicator of technology acceptability is perceived ease of use (Thakur, 2013; Wills, El-Gayar, & Bennett, 2008). In the views of (Davis, Bagozzi, & Warshaw, 1989; Venkatesh et al., 2003), when users of technology perceive usage to be easy, they are inclined to produce a favorable and much stronger intention to use. The findings of a study by (Davis, 1989) underscore the centrality of ease of use which is linked with effort expectancy with regards to technology use. Within the framework of this study, we speculate that nurses' adoption of electronic health records will largely be anchored on their opinion of ease of technology use. As such, the more user-friendly the nurse's perception of the system, the more likely the propensity or inclination. From the foregoing discussion, we suggest that:

Hypothesis 2: Effort expectancy has a significant effect on nurses' behavioral intentions to adopt electronic health records.

Social Influence (SI)

The study defines (SI) as the level referent others approve of nurse's use of electronic health records. Social Influence is theoretically identical to a construct proposed in other prior models,

subjective norm: (Theory of Reasoned Action and, Theory of Planned Behavior). Subjective Norms (SN) refers to social influence for performing or not performing an action, and the drive to conform (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980). Social influence in the framework of a specific innovation use is the motivation that individuals who are vital to you (referent group) think you ought, or ought not to use a system in question. Various research has shown that social influence affects behavioral intentions towards using a system (Albar & Hoque, 2019; Zolait, 2014). Again, social influence is considered to be an effective factor in evaluating innovation acceptance and usage in several studies (Ajzen, 1991; Taylor & Todd, 1995; Venkatesh & Davis, 2000). Based on this account we propose:

Hypothesis 3: Social influence has a significant effect on the nurses' behavioral intentions to adopt electronic health records.

Attitudes towards electronic health records (EHR)

Attitude as described by Ajzen and Fishbein (1977) is nurses' emotional assessment towards using electronic health records. Attitude towards technology can refer to the extent a person enjoys or does not enjoy using that technology. It could also refer to individuals' positive or negative disposition towards an object or technology. The rapport that exists between attitude and intention indicates that nurses' positive attitude toward the use of electronic health records will ultimately affect their behavioral intent to use the technology (Ajzen, 1985). According to Ajzen and Fishbein (1980), individuals' commitment toward performing a behavior is indicated in their intention. This suggests that, whenever an individual or a group regard technology in a positive light, they will be likely to use it. The converse also holds. Against the backdrop of the arguments advanced, we propose that:

H4: Attitudes will have a positive relationship with nurses' behavioral intention to adopt electronic health records.

Design aesthetics (Appearance)

Design aesthetics pertains to the elegance of an artifact's look. As has been the findings of many past studies, the uniqueness, and beauty of a specific new technology is an essential aspect of the influence it will have on the approval of that innovation (Cyr et al., 2006; Dahlgaard et al., 2008). This study describes design aesthetics as how the color, shape, size, and appearance of electronic health records systems and tools may provide a certain artistic, sense of proportion, or attract one's

emotions (Cyr et al., 2006). Distinctiveness will satisfy self-expression needs and improve social values. Electronic health record systems and their tools' design aesthetics are intended to induce users' attention and augment deployment and implementation desire (Hsiao, 2013). Jeong et al. (2017) likewise asserted that design aesthetics is an attractive feature of some systems, which influence its adoption and use. Hence, the resulting hypothesis;

H5: Design aesthetics has a positive relationship with the behavioral intention of nurses to adopt electronic health records.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Methodology

Sample and data collection

The study utilized a questionnaire to draw data to assess the proposed framework and hypotheses. Study participants included qualified health personnel specifically nurses. As such, the nurses were randomly selected from across sixteen different medical centers in the central district of Ghana. This was done with reason to ensure adequate representation. To attain a diverse sample, the nurses

were sampled under a convenience sampling technique. Before data collection, the research team explained the study purpose to respondents and received their approval after which the questionnaires were administered. Moreover, before the commencement of data collection, an experimental study was carried out with 35 respondents from the sampled populace. After the test study, the questionnaire was refined to represent recommendations gathered. Data collection distributed a total of 420 questionnaires. To avoid biases in responses, there were no incentives offered to respondents. Data collection was conducted from April 1st to July 30th, 2020. Upon the collection of the data, the research team reviewed and discarded uncompleted questionnaires. Finally, 381 workable questionnaires remained; this reflected a 91 % response rate. The demographic data of study participants is captured in table 1.

Measures

Research variables were uniformly rated on a 5-point Likert scale extending from “*strongly disagree*” (1) to “*strongly agree*” (5). All measures were adapted from past studies which had proven their validity and reliability of the scale. All queries were closed-ended and intended to meet the five-point Likert scale responses. Modifications were made to questions per study setting. The study developed an English questionnaire, which was partitioned into two parts. The first part captured sociodemographic particulars like; age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, and years of service. The second part captured questions related to study constructs anchored on the proposed study model. It enabled for answers connecting nurses’ adoption intention of electronic health records based on the proposed hypothesis. Online copies of the questionnaires were administered to the nurses who operated at the selected health institutions.

Data analysis method

Given the conceptual model and the proposed hypothesis, the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique, and Analysis of Moments of Structures (AMOS) version 25 was utilized to establish the model and data analysis. Ultimately, the utilization of SEM is anchored on: (a) examining the sequence of dependent variables at once, especially in a situation where direct and indirect effects exist amongst constructs (J. Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2010); (b) Spotting interactions amid variables; (c) modeling variations in observed variables; and (d) Observe latent variables with several indicators (Hoyle, 2011). SEM entails two processes of analysis; thus, the measurement and structural model (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988). Whereas the measurement model was

employed to assess the relations among latent variables and their respective items, the structural model was employed to assess construct interactions. In ensuing data analysis, the study assessed the measurement model to establish the validity and reliability of the constructs. The structural model was further estimated to assess relations amid the proposed hypotheses.

Results

Demographics of respondents

The findings have demonstrated that 69.55% of the respondents were female, 30.45% were male, and 69.82% of all respondents were between the ages of 26 -35 years. Respondents who were married represented 64.30%. Out of the total respondents, 38.06% had a bachelor's degree, 30.71% had a Diploma, and 22.31% had a master's degree. Concerning years of service of the respondents, 43.57% represented respondents who have served for 7years and above.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristic of respondents

Variable	Group	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	116	30.45
	Female	265	69.55
Age	21 - 25	14	3.67
	26 - 35	266	69.82
	36 - 45	84	22.05
	46 - 55	9	2.36
	56 and Above	8	2.10
Marital Status	Married	136	35.70
	Single	245	64.30
Educational Qualification	Masters	85	22.31
	Bachelor	145	38.06
	Diploma	117	30.71
	Others	34	8.92
Years of Service	Less than a year	19	4.99
	1 – 3 years	110	28.87
	4 – 6 years	86	22.57
	7 years and above	166	43.57
Total		381	100

Data analysis

Measurement Model analysis

The study conducted confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to assess the validity and reliability of the proposed model. The outcome reported an adequate and suitable fit amongst the measurement model and the research's dataset. The result of the structural model measured indices such as adjusted goodness of fit index, the goodness of fit index, root mean square error of approximation, normed fit index, comparative fit index, incremental fit index, and the degree of freedom. Table 5 gives evidence that all measurements were of good fit and reliable with suggested values of (Wu, 2010). The model's fitness is in line with the recommended values (Elkaseh, Wong, & Fung, 2016; J. F. Hair, Anderson, Tatham, & Black, 1998). In assessing the reliability of the construct, composite reliability, and Cronbach alpha values were used (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). As captured in table 3 the Cronbach alpha ranged from 0.793 to 0.929. Our results were revealed to be greater than the commended threshold of 0.70, signifying support for the reliability (J. F. Hair et al., 1998). To ascertain the convergent validity, Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and item loadings were used (Chiu & Wang, 2008). As captured in table 2 and table 3, items were all considerably loaded disparately on constructs at a level greater than the commended level of 0.70. The readings of AVE were between 0.708 and 0.874 signifying sufficient reflection and consistency with convergent validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). In testing the discriminant validity, the study compared the relationships amongst AVE values and shared variances among compared constructs (Liu, Ke, Wei, Gu, & Chen, 2010). As captured in table 4 all construct correlations were lesser than the square root of AVE values supporting discriminant validity (Paulraj, Lado, & Chen, 2008). These outcomes reflected the adequacy of reliability, convergent validity, and the discriminant validity of the study outcomes.

Table 2: Item loading and cross loadings

Construct	Item	BI	ATT	PE	SI	EE	AE
Behavioral Intention (BI)	BI1	.950	-.068	.015	-.036	-.012	-.004
	BI2	.933	.052	-.007	-.016	.031	-.014
	BI3	.922	.017	-.012	.054	-.014	.025
Attitude Towards E-Health Records (ATT)	ATT1	.027	.912	-.004	-.034	-.030	-.057
	ATT2	-.035	.912	.005	.027	.038	.041
	ATT3	.004	.896	.001	.005	-.020	.020
Performance Expectancy (PE)	PE1	.042	.082	.870	.014	.027	-.045
	PE2	-.003	-.020	.906	.040	.014	.019
	PE3	-.035	-.049	.950	-.051	-.036	.027
Social Influence (SI)	SI1	.045	-.037	.024	.874	-.056	-.057

	SI2	-.011	-.012	.021	.896	.011	.032
	SI3	-.034	.046	-.044	.886	.044	.028
Effort Expectancy (EE)	EE1	.004	-.039	-.044	-.002	.834	.008
	EE2	.036	-.011	.019	.015	.857	.027
	EE3	-.036	.037	.026	-.011	.878	-.044
Design Aesthetics (AE)	AE1	-.023	-.029	.018	.060	-.012	.807
	AE2	.021	.010	.004	-.079	.035	.890
	AE3	.008	.025	-.016	.022	-.031	.825

Table 3: Convergent Validity and Reliability

Construct	Item	loadings	Cronbach Alpha	CR	AVE
Behavioral Intention (BI)	BI1	.950			
	BI2	.933	.929	0.954	0.874
	BI3	.922			
Attitude Towards E-Health Records (ATT)	ATT1	.912			
	ATT2	.912	.892	0.933	0.822
	ATT3	.896			
Performance Expectancy (PE)	PE1	.870			
	PE2	.906	.897	0.935	0.827
	PE3	.950			
Social Influence (SI)	SI1	.874			
	SI2	.896	.862	0.916	0.784
	SI3	.886			
Effort Expectancy (EE)	EE1	.834			
	EE2	.857	.820	0.892	0.734
	EE3	.878			
Design Aesthetics (AE)	AE1	.807			
	AE2	.890	.793	0.879	0.708
	AE3	.825			

Note: AVE = Average Variance Extracted; CR = Composite Reliability

Table 4: Correlation, Mean and Standard deviation

Construct	Mean	STD	BI	ATT	PE	SI	EE	AE
BI	3.345	1.317	.935					
ATT	3.906	1.018	.313**	.907				
PE	3.530	1.013	.247**	.339**	.909			
SI	4.426	.771	.175**	.047	.001	.885		
EE	3.419	1.016	.119*	-.066	-.059	-.070	.857	
AE	3.588	1.064	.161**	.059	.066	.011	-.028	.841

*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01; **STD** = Standard Deviation

Table 5: Fit Measure for Structural Model

Measurements	Indices	Criterion	Results	
			Structural model	Measurement
Absolute fit measures	AGFI	> .80	.908	.918
	GFI	> .90	.930	.942
	RMSEA	< .08	.052	.045
	NFI	> .90	.933	.946
Incremental fit measures	CFI	> .90	.965	.975
	IFI	> .90	.965	.976
	CMIN/DF	< 3.00	2.036	1.779

AGFI = Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index; **GFI** = Goodness of Fit Index; **RMSEA** = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation; **NFI** = Normed Fit Index; **CFI** = Comparative Fit Index; **IFI** = Incremental Fit Index; **CMIN/DF** = Chi-square/Degree of freedom

Structural model and hypothesis testing results

Given the proposed study model and items, the structural model is established to ascertain the path relationship of study constructs. After demonstrating the validity of the measurement model, the presented hypotheses were verified. The path analysis of the structural model is presented in Table 6. The finding proved that PE → BI ($\beta = 0.194^{**}$, $t = 3.217$, $p < 0.01$), EE → BI ($\beta = 0.261^{***}$, $t = 3.452$, $p < 0.001$) and SI → BI ($\beta = 0.377^{***}$, $t = 3.900$, $p < 0.001$), all have a substantial relation with behavioral intention toward electronic health records. These results are consistent with the proposed H1, H2, and H3. Finally, ATT → BI ($\beta = 0.380^{***}$, $t = 5.712$, $p < 0.001$), and AE → BI ($\beta = 0.217^{**}$, $t = 3.048$, $p < 0.001$), also showed that attitude and aesthetic design respectively have a positive relationship with nurses' intent to use electronic health records. The outcomes were a confirmation of H4 and H5. Summarily, our results indicated all hypotheses were significant, and as such sufficiently supported. It also, explained a medium to large effect of Ghanaian nurses' behavior intention to adopt electronic health records (Cohen, 1988).

Table 6: Path Analysis of Structural Model

Path	β	t-statistics	Hypothesis	Interpretation
PE → BI	.194**	3.217	H1	Supported
EE → BI	.261***	3.452	H2	Supported
SI → BI	.377***	3.900	H3	Supported
ATT → BI	.380***	5.712	H4	Supported
AE → BI	.217**	3.048	H5	Supported
R²				
BI	.219			

** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$;

Discussion

All research hypotheses were confirmed as shown in Table 6. The study employed the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). The results confirmed the appropriateness of the main concepts represented in the UTAUT. Additional technology-specific variables (attitude toward use and design aesthetics) were further incorporated into this aforementioned theory, to investigate nurses' intention to use electronic health records. The outcome confirms not only the robustness of the adopted theory but also, that of the proposed research model. The reports also consistently reinforced the added constructs, representative of the impact of attitude and design aesthetics on the behavioral intention toward electronic health record system use. Performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and social influence thus positively impact nurses' use intent with regards to the electronic health records. Therefore, a better experience of the electronic health record system will allow nurses to improve efficiency and to increase the value of their work. Regarding our study findings, it was indicated that performance expectancy has a substantial relationship with the behavioral intent of nurses towards electronic health records use. The outcome of this result could be interpreted to mean that, whenever nurses find merit, and as such, relevance in using electronic health records, they will consider the technology and develop an intention to use. Precisely, the formation of use intention is likely to be predicated on factors including but not limited to the system efficacy and responsiveness to meet the health needs of users. This finding confirmed our proposed study hypothesis H1. The results are in line with previous studies (Holtz & Krein, 2011; Ifinedo, 2012).

Furthermore, our study established effort expectancy to have a substantial relationship with behavioral intent to use. This outcome confirmed the proposed hypotheses H2. An explanation of this outcome could imply that nurses' responsiveness to the ease of use and user-friendliness of electronic health records significantly affects their overall positive evaluation of the system. Whereas a positive evaluation of (regarding the dearth of difficulty in technology use) is prone to enhance a positive attitude, and possibly translate into an intention to use, the converse is also likely to work against electronic health record use. This finding further underscores the potency of user comfort and convenience underpinning the decision process relative to health technology use. For this reason, it is prudent that the pursuit of health service quality takes into cognizance factors such as system quality. This finding echoes the proposition of (Kijisanayotin et al., 2009).

Moving on, the results further revealed social influence to have a substantial relationship with behavior intention to use electronic health records, signifying support for the hypothesis H3. Social influence is conceptualized as the degree of external push or influence on people to conform to a certain behavior. This pressure emanates from individuals regarded as important or relevant to the user. Where nursing staff anticipates and understands medical administration expects them to use electronic health record systems, they are motivated to use the system and to cope better with the associated stress. This outcome submits that persons will probably execute a behavior (i.e. electronic health record adoption) when they perceive expectations from a referent group to adopt. Our results are consistent with previous research (Ahmad & Khalid, 2017; Kohnke, Cole, Bush, & innovation, 2014; Zuiderwijk, Janssen, & Dwivedi, 2015).

Also, the results revealed attitude to be significantly related to behavioral intention. This supports H4. Attitude refers to the level of nurses' correct or incorrect appraisal of the use of electronic health records (Choi & Kim, 2016). Linking the finding in the context of our study, nurses' attitude toward electronic health records was positively related to behavioral intention due to the favorable appraisal of its usage. If prospective users take a positive view of technology, they are likely to adopt that specific technology or innovation. To buttress this point, (Beck & Ajzen, 1991) assert that, the higher the users' attitude toward technology, the stronger the intent to use the technology or perform the action. On the contrary, the lower the significance to the user, the weaker the possibility for the user to act. While a negative user assessment will impede the use of technological innovation, a positive evaluation will explicitly develop and promote the development of a strong use behavior, that further reinforces a firm intention to use (Fathema, Shannon, & Ross, 2015). (Arkorful et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2012) reiterate the association between attitude and behavioral intention.

Again, the results revealed the design aesthetics (appearance) of electronic health record systems substantially related to behavioral intention to use. This echoes the support of hypothesis H5. The scholarship describes design aesthetics as how the color, shape, size, and appearance of electronic health record systems and tools may provide certain artistic, sense of proportion, or attract one's emotions (Cyr et al., 2006). The uniqueness and beauty of a particular technology is an essential factor in the influence it will have on the acceptance of that technology or innovation (Cyr et al., 2006; Dahlgaard et al., 2008). Uniqueness of a system will gratify needs for self-expression and

create overall usage satisfaction. That is to say that, the appealing and attractive nature of electronic health records systems and tools to nurses affects their behavioral intent toward usage. The outcome of our study is consistent with (Jeong et al., 2017).

Study limitations and future research

Irrespective of the strengths of the study in the prior section, the study has some shortcomings outlined which are necessary to serve as a blueprint to assist future research. Test samples from different areas in Ghana were collected for the study. Though the totality of the sample size is adequate with regards to our study context, generalizing of the outcome and replicating it in another domain should be done with reservation. Due to the diversity with which technology is accepted in different areas, adoption intention may equally vary from one place to the other. On this basis, we suggest future studies to consider specific health structures in certain administrative regions and strongly recommend future studies to draw cross-sectional data or use longitudinal data to investigate the subject matter under investigation. Our study employed a quantitative method. In this respect, we recommend future research to employ a mixed-method involving qualitative and quantitative data and also face to face interviews to generate and acquire more in-depth responses from the participants on their intention to use a system. Another limitation was the cost involved in the research as no funding was granted to the researchers. These limitations do not however invalidate the study findings.

Conclusion

Nurses form an important part of the workforce of their respective health institutions. Acceptance of the electronic health record systems and related technologies by nurses is believed to benefit the hospital service delivery, specifically, advancements in nursing care offered, and in the quality of nursing personnel performance. The study presented a valuable insight for health administrators to help in the assessment of the probable success of innovative technology like electronic health records and enlighten nurses to comprehend the paybacks of its usage. Using the UTUAT incorporated with additional variables (i.e. attitude and design aesthetics), our study investigates nurses' intention to use electronic health records in Ghana using the structural equation modeling technique. To enhance comprehension of nurse's adoption intention, our study proposed a model to test its robustness. Our study confirmed the relevance of relationships among all study constructs.

The outcome implies that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and social influence all impacts nurse's behavioral intent towards electronic health records. Furthermore, attitude and design aesthetics were also revealed to influence the behavioral intent of nurses to use electronic health records. The combination of design aesthetics, attitude toward use, and the SEM relationship gives this study additional originality. Although a large number of studies have used SEM to assess and validate the theoretical framework, health innovation studies model has rarely been used. SEM is used primarily for model testing and helps to simplify the difficulty of adoption models in the context of a technology. Therefore, our study utilizes the SEM approach to analyze the hypotheses and to establish factual predictors, whilst indicating predictors as inputs for effective and efficient policy. The study offers relevant theoretical and feasible implications for academics, scholars, stakeholders in the health sector, and other entities with the health sector working relationship.

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Conflict of interest

The submission of this manuscript does not pose possible conflicts of interest

Appendix A. measures

Performance Expectancy (PE) (Kijasanayotin et al., 2009; Venkatesh et al., 2003)

PE1: I find electronic health records useful to my job

PE2: Using electronic health records will aid me to perform tasks more quickly.

PE3: Using electronic health records will boost my efficiency.

Effort Expectancy (EE) (Venkatesh, Thong, & Xu, 2012)

EE1: My interaction with electronic health records would be clear and understandable

EE2: It would be easy for me to become skillful at using electronic health records

EE3: I would find electronic health records easy to use

Social Influence (SI) (Kijasanayotin et al., 2009; Venkatesh et al., 2012)

SI1: I believe that important referents think I should use electronic health records

SI2: My working environment influences my intention to use electronic health records

SI3: In general, the hospital administration encourages and support the use of electronic health records in health care provision

Design Aesthetics (Choi & Kim, 2016; Hsiao, 2013)

AE1: I am satisfied with the simple design of electronic health record systems

AE2: The display size of an electronic health record system and tools does not cause any inconvenience in its usage.

AE3: I am satisfied with the color and shape of the electronic health record systems.

Attitude toward the use of e-health systems and tools (Choi & Kim, 2016; Hsiao, 2013)

ATT1: Using electronic health records is a good healthcare delivery intervention

ATT2: I will enjoy using electronic health records

ATT3: I will be satisfied with using electronic health records

Behavioral Intention to Use Electronic health records

(Davis, 1989; Sarwar, Zulfiqar, Aziz, & Ejaz Chandia, 2019)

BI1: I intend to use electronic health records

BI2: I predict I will use electronic health records

BI3: Electronic health records will be one of my favorite health technology interventions.

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